

ISSUES STUDYING MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation: *This article deals with issues related to the study of medical terminology by national students in medical universities.*

Keywords: *anatomical terminology, Latin terms, etymological, semantic and morphological features.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada tibbiyot Oliygo'harida milliy guruhi talabalari tomonidan tibbiy terminologiyani o'rganish bilan bog'liq masalalar ko'rib chiqilgan.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *anatomik atamalar, lotin atamalari, etimologik, semantik va morfologik belgilar.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с изучением национальными студентами медицинских терминологий в медицинских вузах.*

Ключевые слова: *анатомическая терминология, латинские термины, этимологические, семантические и морфологические особенности.*

Lexis and their latinization, etymological, semantic and morphological features

Nomina si nescis, perit et cognitio rerum - if you do not know the names, then the knowledge of things is lost. This famous aphorism of Carl Linnaeus, who gave the world a binary system of botanical names, applies to all types of terminology, including medical terminology. The scientific formulation of the term and its definition is the fundamental basis of the doctor's competence, which

develops not only in the process of many years of study of the future specialist, but also in subsequent years in the process of improving his qualifications. And if while studying at his university for a student, the first source of acquiring terminological definitions was a textbook, and last but not least, a textbook on medical Latin, then later such a source and standard of scientific names of terms, their interpretations and information on the history of their origin becomes a dictionary - reference literature. The benefits of such dictionaries, especially explanatory etymological ones, are also spoken by the doctors themselves, who prepared the “Concise Explanatory Dictionary of Medical Terms” [4]. In this paper, we would like to draw the attention of such enthusiastic doctors and linguists working on the creation of dictionary and reference literature to the problem of the quality of etymological information.

An etymological reference is an important part of information about a term that contributes to a more conscious perception of its semantics, and it is not by chance that in the most authoritative foreign dictionaries of medical terminology (Butterworths Medical Dictionary, Dorland's Illustrated Medical Dictionary, Stedman's Medical Dictionary) an etymological reference is attached to each term (by the way, we use this fact as a strong argument confirming the need to study the Greek-Latin foundations of modern international terminology in teaching a course of medical Latin in groups of English-speaking students). Realizing this, the authors of domestic dictionaries and reference publications volens-nolens in some cases resort to etymological references, although it is obvious that the best solution to the problem would be to provide etymological information for each term. Pharmaceutical terms are especially in need of an etymological component, the number of which outstrips the growth of terms in other biomedical sciences. The complexity of the problem lies in the fact that the etymology of many terms is far from always clear to doctors or pharmacists themselves, and linguistic commentary on new terms in reference literature is often decades behind the appearance and everyday use of terms. And even in the popular Wikipedia, which tries to keep up with the times, etymological references to new terms are not always provided. In

addition, etymological references in such reference literature are often inaccurate or do not correspond to the truth at all. Here are two examples from the Concise Explanatory Dictionary of Medical Terms mentioned above. US. 114 The compilers of the dictionary correctly associate the term diabetes with the Greek noun diabetes, but interpret it as a water pipe, siphon, while the correct meaning of this word in this case is transition. After all, the Greek noun diabetes is a derivative of the verb diabaino with the meaning to pass, to step over and literally means to pass, step over. The ancient Greek physician Areteus of Cappadocia, who introduced this term, called this term the phenomenon of diabetes - the rapid passage of fluid through the body of a person with diabetes. On page 239, the term splenium bandage is explained as a derivative of the Greek adjective splen dense, although such a word is not recorded either in the well-known dictionary of the ancient Greek language by I.Kh. Dvoretzky [2], nor in the most complete lexicon of the ancient Greek language today

Liddell Scott Jones. And in the etymological dictionary of the Latin language Ernu-Meie, the noun splenium is unambiguously derived from the Greek splenion bandage or plaster for a diseased spleen, derived from splen spleen. Examples of such etymological inaccuracies can often be found, not to mention journal publications or the media, and in reputable academic publications. For example, in L.P. Krysin's Explanatory Dictionary of Foreign Words, the author explains to the reader that the term "insulin", derived from the Latin insula island, got its name due to the fact that the pancreas, in which insulin is produced, "was metaphorically likened to an island [3, p. 306]. However, it is well known that the name of this pancreatic hormone got its name due to the fact that it is produced by a group of special cells of the pancreas, called the islets of Langerhans. In the same dictionary we read that the term "Trichomonas" is derived from the Greek word trachoma hair" [3, c.795].

However, the term "trichomonas" (Latin equivalent of trichomōnas, ādis f), according to the compilers of the Butterworth's medical dictionary mentioned above [5, p. 1748], as well as the equally well-known dictionary of medical terms

by G. Arnaudov [1, p. 531], compiled on the basis of two Greek words - thrix, trichos hair and monas, monados odi

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